

Original Article

Childhood Pneumonia: A 5-Year Review of Types, Presentation and Treatment Outcome in a Tertiary Hospital in South-South Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Childhood pneumonia is the number one leading cause of under-five mortality in the world today and it accounted for more than 800,000 deaths in the year 2018. The study aims to determine the hospital prevalence of pneumonia, the types and the treatment outcome of affected children in the Delta State University Teaching Hospital in the last 5 years. The study was a review of the cases of pneumonia admitted into the Paediatric Department of the Delta State University Teaching Hospital (DELSUTH) in the last 5 years. All cases managed for pneumonia in the department were identified by hospital number and the folders retrieved. Data such as age, gender, weight, nutritional status, social class, immunization status, presenting symptoms, duration of symptoms, signs, chest radiograph findings and treatment outcome were documented. The diagnosis of pneumonia was based on the presence of cough, fast breathing or chest indrawing in children less than 5 years. Data was entered into Microsoft Excel Spreadsheet and was analyzed. There were 897 children seen over the period under review with 468 (52.2%) males and 429 (47.8%) females. The hospital prevalence of pneumonia was 4.0% and it occurred mainly in infants. Bronchopneumonia was the predominant presentation with lobar pneumonias occurring only in children less than 2 years of age. The overall treatment outcome of pneumonia was good. The hospital prevalence of childhood pneumonia among admitted children was low and occurred mainly in infants. Bronchopneumonia was the commonest presentation, and the treatment outcome of affected children was good

Keywords: Childhood, Pneumonia, Southern, Nigeria

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INTRODUCTION

Childhood pneumonia is the number one leading cause of under-five mortality in the world today accounting for more than 800,000 deaths in the year 2018.¹ Only five countries accounted for more than 50% of deaths recorded from pneumonia in 2019 and they included the following from the highest to the lowest:

Nigeria (162,000), India (127,000), Pakistan (58,000), the Democratic Republic of Congo (40,000) and Ethiopia (32,000).² Also, 19% of under-five deaths in Nigeria were due to pneumonia in 2018.¹ The prevalence of death was highest among children between the ages of 1-2 years.³ The mortality is worse in the setting of overcrowding, malnutrition and immune-suppression like HIV.^{4,5} Other documented risk factors include prematurity, formula fed infants, air pollution, small for gestational age, low socio-economic class, airway abnormalities, congenital heart diseases, CNS disorders and so on.^{4,6}

Pneumonia has been described in recent times as the forgotten epidemic.^{7,8} Pernille Ironside, the UNICEF representative in Nigeria described pneumonia as a deadly disease that has been forgotten on the global and national health agendas.¹ Evidently, global and national funding for pneumonia is on the decline, and presently very low. Only 3% of current global infectious disease research spending is allocated to pneumonia, despite the fact that it causes about 15% of deaths in children under-five years of age.¹

Despite these abysmal indices, pneumonias can be largely prevented with vaccines, and treatment can be effective with low-cost antibiotics if promptly diagnosed.^{1,9,10} There was a renewed call by UNICEF and its partners to all stakeholders to carry out more research on pneumonia, and increase funding of vaccines against pneumonia.¹ The present study was carried out to review the burden of childhood pneumonia in Delta State University Teaching Hospital in the last five years in order to reawaken the consciousness of stakeholders to this deadly and forgotten epidemic.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was carried out in Delta State University Teaching Hospital (DELSUTH), Oghara. Delta state is one of the 36 states of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. It is located in the south-south geopolitical region of

Nigeria and in the oil rich region of the Niger Delta. The DELSUTH is a tertiary hospital with a bedding capacity of 205. It serves as a referral centre for primary and secondary health facilities in the Delta Central and Delta South senatorial districts of the state.

The study population comprised of children admitted into the Paediatric Department of the DELSUTH from 2015-2019. Ethical approval was obtained from the Ethics committee of the DELSUTH. The study was a review of the cases admitted into the department of Paediatrics in DELSUTH in the last 5 years. Children whose data were incomplete or missing were excluded from the study. All cases managed for pneumonia in the Paediatric department were identified by hospital number and their folders were retrieved. Data such as age, gender, weight, nutritional status, social class and immunization status were documented. Other data collected included presenting symptoms, duration of symptoms, signs, chest radiograph findings and treatment outcome. Diagnosis of pneumonia was based on cough, fast breathing or chest in drawing with or without fever provided the child is under-five. All children were required to do chest x-ray and the presence of pneumonic infiltrates was required to confirm the diagnosis of pneumonia in children above 5 years. Data was entered into Microsoft Excel Spreadsheet and was analyzed.

RESULTS

There were 897 children seen during the period under review out of which 468 (52.2%) were males and 429 (47.8%) were females. Two hundred and eight (32.0%) were infants, 377 (42.0%) were between ages 1-5years and 312 (26.0%) were children above 5 years as seen in table I.

Thirty-five (4.0%) cases of pneumonia were seen during the period under review. Twenty-three (65.7%) cases of pneumonia occurred in males while 12 (34.3%) occurred in females. Twenty-five (71.4%) cases occurred in children less than 1 year, 7 (20.0%)

cases occurred in children between the ages of 1-5 years, and only 3 (8.6%) cases occurred in children older than 5 years as seen in figure 1. Also, there were 3 (8.6%) cases of lobar pneumonia and 32 (91.4%) cases of bronchopneumonia in the present study with all the cases of lobar pneumonia occurring in children less than 2 years of age.

Table I: Gender, Age and Social Class Distribution in DELSUTH

Variable	N (%)
Sex	
Male	468 (52.2)
Female	429 (47.8)
Age	
Infants	208 (32.0)
1- 5 years	377 (42.0)
≥ 5 years	312 (26.0)
Social Class	
Upper	077 (8.6)
Middle	717 (80.0)
Lower	103 (11.4)
NPI Immunization status	
Fully immunized for age	30 (85.7)
Not immunized	05 (14.3)

NPI- National program on immunization

Figure 1: Distribution of pneumonia among the different age groups

Seventeen (47.2%) children who had pneumonia were EBF while the others were not EBF as seen in figure 2. Among children between 6 months and 5 years with pneumonia, 7 (38.8%) had normal weight; 8 (44.4%) were underweight and 3 (16.7%) were marasmic as seen in figure 3.

Figure 2: Proportion of children with pneumonia that were exclusively breastfed (EBF) versus non exclusively breastfed children (NEBF)

Figure 3: Weight classification of children with pneumonia

Co-morbidity associated with pneumonia from the present study included 7 (20.0%) cases of heart failure, 4 (11.4%) severe anaemia, and 1 (2.9%) case each of pleural effusion, pericardial effusion and respiratory failure.

Out of the 35 children with pneumonia, 8 (22.9%) children had low SPO₂ with values less than 94% and 27 (77.1%) children had crepitations on chest auscultation.

However, all the children had fast breathing or labored breathing as evidenced by either flaring of the ala nasi, trachea tugging, or chest in-drawing as shown in figure 4.

There were 29 (82.8%) discharges, 3(8.6%) referred cases and 3(8.6%) cases were discharged against medical advice.

Figure 4: Clinical features of children with pneumonia in DELSUTH

DISCUSSION

The prevalence of pneumonia over 5 year period in the present study was 4.0%. This is less than the reported prevalence of 9.0% in the same facility about a decade ago before the introduction of the Hib and the PCV vaccines.¹¹The prevalence is lower than the prevalence of 13.3% reported in Ilorin, Northcentral Nigeria.¹² However, the prevalence is comparable to the prevalence of 4.7% reported in Sokoto, Northwestern Nigeria.¹³ The low prevalence does not imply that pneumonia is rare in children at the study centre because being a referral centre, most cases of pneumonia would have been seen and managed at the primary and secondary health centres in the state.

The present study showed that though infants constituted only about a third of the total admitted cases seen, yet they contributed more than two-third of the

cases of pneumonia seen during the study period. A similar finding has been reported by other authors both locally and globally.¹²⁻¹⁶ The reason why infants are more prone to pneumonia cases than older children is most likely due to immaturity of the innate and acquired immunity.¹⁷ Other risk factors for childhood pneumonia reported in the literatures include malnutrition, poor immunization and lack of exclusive breastfeeding among others.¹⁸ About a quarter of children from the present study were not fully immunized and more than half of affected children were either malnourished or not exclusively breastfed.

About two-third of pneumonia cases in the present study occurred in males and this pattern has been reported by other authors.^{12,19,20} Other forms of sepsis have also been shown to occur more in males though the reason for this finding is not quite certain.²¹

Bronchopneumonia occurred more frequently accounting for more than 80% of cases in the present study. Bronchopneumonia has been reported by other authors to be more frequent in under-five.¹²⁻¹⁴ Also, less than 10% cases were due to lobar pneumonia and occurred only in children less than 2 years of age. This category of children with lobar pneumonia are more likely due to bacterial pneumonia like *Streptococcus pneumoniae*,¹⁸ but unfortunately, blood culture from these children yielded no growth. The negative blood culture in this category of patients may be due to the fact that most of these children were referred from primary and secondary health centres where they were given antibiotics before presenting to the study facility.

Fever, cough and fast breathing/chest in-drawing were the commonest clinical features reported in the present study. These symptoms have been reported by other authors and remain very useful in the early diagnosis of pneumonia in primary and secondary health facilities so as to ensure early referral to a tertiary health facility.^{12-14,22} Crepitations occurred at a lower prevalence especially among the very young infants possibly due to poor localization of symptoms in this group of children.²³ Only about 22% cases of pneumonia were

severe enough to present with low SPO₂.

More than 80% of cases were discharged and no mortality was recorded in the present study. This is a complete departure from studies from other parts of Nigeria where mortality has been reported in the range of 10-20%.¹²⁻¹⁴ The reasons for the favourable treatment outcome from the present study is not certain, but probably most severe cases did not make it from the primary and secondary facility to the study centre before they died. While under-five treatment in the primary and secondary health facilities in Delta state is free, treatment of under-five in the tertiary facility is not free, and this could have reduced the number of pneumonia cases seen in the present study. Also, the previous studies were done before the inclusion of Hib and PCV into the immunization schedule while the present study was done after the initiation of these vaccines into the national program on immunization (NPI). Therefore, it is very likely that mortality from pneumonia has declined in the last 5-10 years since the introduction of these vaccines.

Also, 3 (8.6%) children were discharged against medical advice by their parents due to inability to continue to pay for their treatment at the study centre. Since there was no record of their return to the health facility for follow up, it was not possible to determine the treatment outcome for these children. Therefore, the treatment outcome of the present study could not have reflected the true burden of deaths from childhood pneumonia in this environment.

CONCLUSION

The prevalence of childhood pneumonia from the present study is low. The disease condition was found predominantly in infants with bronchopneumonia been the commonest type. The treatment outcome is apparently favourable, but unlikely to reflect the true outcome of childhood pneumonia in the environment.

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